

A Gain-Scheduled \mathcal{H}_∞ Control Law for a Tailless Aircraft

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Abstract

Linear parameter varying (LPV) control theory is used to design a gain-scheduled \mathcal{H}_∞ flight control law for a tailless fighter aircraft. To compensate for the reduced directional stability, the aircraft under consideration has a large number of multi-axis control effectors. A previous gain-scheduled control law design for this tailless aircraft used simple LPV models that allow for straightforward computation of the controller gains but may sacrifice performance of the resulting control law. This paper describes a new design that incorporates a higher fidelity LPV model in the design process.

1 Introduction

In [13], a gain-scheduled \mathcal{H}_∞ control law was designed for a tailless fighter aircraft model using linear parameter varying (LPV) control theory. Specifically, the dimensional stability derivatives of the linearized models found at trimmed equilibrium conditions were approximated by linear and quadratic functions of dynamic pressure to form an LPV model. Using the results of [3, 4, 5], an automatically gain-scheduled LPV controller was then found. Although the results showed promise, the LPV model was made somewhat simplistic to allow straightforward computation of the controller. In this paper, we extend the results of [13] by using a more detailed, higher fidelity model of the tailless fighter aircraft.

The aircraft of interest has a large number of multi-axis control effectors to account for its reduced directional control power. The approach taken in this paper is to use a modular control law architecture, separating the control design process from the control allocation process, to design a control law for the tailless aircraft. Since the aircraft has multiple control effectors that affect both longitudinal and lateral-directional axes, the control law will be designed using generalized moment commands in the state space models. The control law will then be implemented with a control selector to combine the commands for each axis to the multi-axis control effectors.

LPV control design techniques have been applied to flying vehicles before. In [14], the technique of [1] was expanded and applied to the longitudinal axis of a conventional fighter aircraft. Furthermore, the technique of [3, 4, 5] has been used in [2] for a missile autopilot and in [10] for the longitudinal and lateral-directional axes of a conventional fighter aircraft.

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2 LPV Systems

Recently, there has been considerable interest in the design of control laws for linear parameter varying systems [12]. These are linear systems whose coefficients depend on some varying parameters. Consider the system

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}(t) &= A(\theta)x(t) + B(\theta)u(t), \\ y(t) &= C(\theta)x(t) + D(\theta)u(t),\end{aligned}$$

where the parameter vector θ is a function of time that is *a priori* unknown but with known bounds. When the parameter vector θ is constant, this system is simply a linear time-invariant system, for which a wide variety of control design approaches exist. The traditional approach to gain scheduling is to find a control law for a number of fixed values of θ and then to use *ad hoc* procedures to vary the control law gains as θ varies.

The LPV control design problem is to find a control law that depends explicitly in some way on the parameter vector θ . By guaranteeing stability for all values of θ having a specified bound, the stability of the closed loop system is guaranteed. Similarly, by guaranteeing that some performance criteria are met for all θ , the closed loop performance can be guaranteed. Hence, the innovation in LPV control design is the characterization of the controller as an *explicit* function of the varying parameters, yielding an automatically gain-scheduled controller.

There are two main approaches to linear parameter varying control design that have been considered in the literature. The first represents the parameters in a linear fractional interconnection with a nominal system [1] in the same way that system uncertainty is usually represented in robust control design. The second approach involves the use of a single quadratic Lyapunov function to guarantee the stability of the closed loop system [2, 3, 4]. The varying parameters are not represented in a feedback loop as in [1]; instead, the system is represented as an explicit function of the parameters. The framework of [8] is again used to again find a set of solvability conditions for the LPV controller, but now the varying parameters are not treated as uncertain elements in a feedback loop but rather are treated directly. Hence, the conservatism of [1] incurred by allowing the parameters to be complex is overcome, but at the expense of a much more complicated optimization problem. Specifically, the convex constraints must hold for *all* values of the varying parameters, and hence the optimization problem is one with an infinite number of constraints. The problem is made numerically tractable by gridding the parameter space and solving the problem with the constraints only at the grid points. Extensions include the characterization of the problem with

bounded parameter variation rates [5, 15]; these results will be applied to the problem considered in this paper.

3 Tailless Control Law Design

In this section, an LPV model of the tailless aircraft over the subsonic flight envelope is formed and control laws for the longitudinal and lateral directional axes are computed. It is assumed that the dynamics of the different axes are decoupled so that the designs can be done independently. Although many of the innovative control effectors produce moments in both the longitudinal and lateral-directional axes, the use of generalized moment commands and a separate control allocation module allows the different axes to be treated separately. In each case, the control laws are found using an implicit model following structure in the LPV framework to meet closed loop flying qualities requirements. Linear and nonlinear responses demonstrate the closed loop performance.

3.1 LPV Model

Here, we consider the tailless aircraft described in [11, 13]. The aerodynamic data for this model were obtained through wind tunnel tests and the nonlinear equations of motion are implemented in a detailed FORTRAN simulation. Ten state linear models are obtained by trimming the aircraft model in level flight and linearizing the equations of motion at a number of points throughout the flight envelope. For the inner loop control law design, the ten state linear models are truncated to five states corresponding to the short period, roll and Dutch roll modes. The points at which the model was linearized are marked with an \circ in Figure 1. The gap between the points at Mach 0.5 and 0.6 is to account for a discontinuity in the data between high and low speeds resulting from separate low and high speed wind tunnel testing.

Figure 1: Flight Conditions used for LPV Model

The aircraft has a large number of multi-axis control effectors to compensate for the reduced yaw control ef-

fectiveness. Specifically, control effectors include a pitch flap, pitch and yaw thrust vectoring, and left and right elevons, all moving tips, spoiler-slot deflectors and leading edge flaps. For the control law design the control surface deflections are replaced by the generalized moment commands q_c , p_c , and r_c . The linear models have the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\alpha} \\ \dot{q} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_\alpha & 1 \\ M_\alpha & M_q \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ q \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ q_c \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\beta} \\ \dot{p} \\ \dot{r} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_\beta & Y_p & Y_r \\ L_\beta & L_p & L_r \\ N_\beta & N_p & N_r \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta \\ p \\ r \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ p_c \\ r_c \end{bmatrix}.$$

Note that the notation used here for the dimensional derivatives is slightly different from standard notation. The control synthesis will be done using these generalized commands, and the resulting control laws will then be combined with a control selector to translate the generalized control commands to the individual surface commands.

The linear parameter varying model is formed by approximating the dimensional derivatives from these linear models as polynomial functions using a least squares fit. Specifically, each dimensional derivative was fit to a set of basis functions to represent the variation in dynamics across the flight envelope. In this case, the basis functions used were $(1, M, h, M^2, h^2, Mh)$, where M is Mach number and h is the altitude in tens of thousands of feet. Figure 2 shows the approximations of some dimensional derivatives for eight flight conditions not used in the curve fitting, along with the values of the derivatives found using direct linearization at those points. In each case, the approximation is very close.

Figure 2: Curve Fits to Aerodynamic Derivatives

To reduce the computational burden of computing the controller, a subset of the flight conditions shown in Figure 1 is used in the control law synthesis. Specifically, approximate dimensional derivatives at the points marked with an \times in Figure 1 are used for control law synthesis. Furthermore, the rates of variation of Mach number and altitude were bounded for the set of flight conditions used

in the design based on airspeed and excess thrust available. The ranges of Mach and altitude rates (in kft/sec) are shown in Figure 3 for the design points.

Figure 3: Parameter Rate Bounds

3.2 Longitudinal Design

The goal of the longitudinal control law is to provide desirable flying qualities in the pitch axis. Toward this end, a pitch axis controlled variable is chosen as a combination of pitch rate and angle of attack. The pitch axis controlled variable is defined to be

$$MCV = q + K_\alpha \alpha,$$

where K_α is chosen to be a linear function of dynamic pressure. This combination is chosen to be approximately equal to $q + n_z/V_{co}$, where V_{co} is the airspeed at which pitch rate and normal acceleration make equal contributions to the controlled variable [9].

A proportional plus integral control architecture is chosen to provide good steady state as well as maneuvering performance. The proportional plus integral network is achieved using

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_i &= \frac{K_B^2}{4}(MCV_{cmd} - MCV), \\ e &= \frac{K_B}{2}MCV_{cmd} - K_B MCV + x_i. \end{aligned}$$

This proportional plus integral structure has been used with a dynamic inversion control law, which subtracts off the actual dynamics to effectively create a pure integration, to achieve good handling qualities [6]. In that case, the closed loop first order response for the case of perfect inversion is the first order response

$$\frac{MCV}{MCV_{cmd}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}K_B}{s + \frac{1}{2}K_B},$$

where K_B is the crossover frequency of the loop transfer function. Hence, this is the ideal model used in an implicit

model matching synthesis model to achieve good handling qualities.

Pitch rate and angle of attack, as well as the output e of the PI network are used as inputs to the control law. The weighted norm of the error between the ideal model output and the LPV model output, where the weight is chosen to be

$$W_{perf}(s) = \frac{10}{s + 0.1},$$

is minimized. The crossover K_B is chosen to be 5. Input multiplicative uncertainty is included in the synthesis model to account for errors in the wind tunnel data and errors in representing the aircraft model as an LPV system. The weight used for the uncertainty is chosen as

$$W_{unc}(s) = \frac{3s + 1}{5s + 100}.$$

Finally, first order actuator dynamics on the generalized pitch command given by

$$\frac{q_c}{q_{c_{cmd}}} = \frac{20.2}{s + 20.2}$$

are included and measurement noise with intensity 0.1 and 0.05 for the α and q measurements, respectively, is added.

The matrices R and S are chosen to have the form

$$\begin{aligned} R &= R_0 + R_M M + R_h h + R_{M2} M^2 \\ &\quad + R_{h2} h^2 + R_{Mh} Mh, \\ S &= S_0, \end{aligned}$$

so that the matrices R_0 , R_M , R_h , R_{M2} , R_{h2} , R_{Mh} , and S_0 become the unknowns to be found in the LPV optimization problem [3, 4, 5]. The linear parameter varying control law is found by minimizing γ subject to the LMIs from [5], evaluated at the Mach numbers and altitudes corresponding to the flight conditions shown in Figure 1. The real part of the eigenvalues of the fixed parameter closed loop dynamics matrix is constrained to be greater than -40 to eliminate very fast controller poles that could not be implemented in a digital computer. The synthesis model was seventh order and hence results in a seventh order control law.

3.3 Lateral-Directional Design

Analogous to the longitudinal axis, the purpose of the lateral-directional control law is to provide desirable flying qualities in the roll and yaw axes. Roll and yaw controlled variables are chosen as

$$\begin{aligned} LCV &= p \cos \alpha + r \sin \alpha, \\ NCV &= -\beta - p \sin \alpha + r \cos \alpha. \end{aligned}$$

As with the pitch controlled variables, proportional plus integral networks were used in the roll and yaw axes. The ideal models for the model matching control law design are chosen as

$$\frac{LCV}{LCV_{cmd}} = \frac{NCV}{NCV_{cmd}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}K_B}{s + \frac{1}{2}K_B},$$

with $K_B = 5$, as before. The weights on the model matching error and input multiplicative uncertainty are the same as the longitudinal axis. Although a first order actuator model was used successfully with the longitudinal design, a similar model was insufficient for the lateral directional axis. When the resulting design is used with a higher fidelity model of the actuator, the resulting responses are very oscillatory. Hence, a second order model of the actuators given by

$$\frac{p_c}{p_{cmd}} = \frac{r_c}{r_{cmd}} = \frac{0.03s^2 - 7.92s + 830.33}{s^2 + 52.17 + 858.09}$$

is used in the roll and yaw generalized input path in the control law design. Finally, measurement noise is included in the synthesis model with intensity 0.1 for β and 0.05 for p and r .

The uncertain matrices R and S are chosen to have the form

$$\begin{aligned} R &= R_0 + R_M M + R_h h + R_{M2} M^2, \\ S &= S_0, \end{aligned}$$

where the matrices R_0 , R_M , R_h , R_{M2} , and S_0 become the unknowns in the LPV optimization problem. Again, the control optimization problem was solved by minimizing γ subject to a set of LMIs. The synthesis model was fifteenth order and hence results in a fifteenth order control law.

4 Tailless Control Law Analysis

In this section, the LPV control laws found in the previous section are analyzed. In order to get a representative sampling of the behavior across the flight envelope, five operating points are chosen to represent the range of operating points in the subsonic envelope. The five points chosen are listed in Table 1 and are chosen to be points not used in the control law synthesis. In addition, aircraft data, rather than the approximate LPV aircraft model, is used in the analysis.

M	h (ft)	\bar{q} (psi)	V (ft/sec)
0.35	15,000	102.45	370.05
0.45	5,000	249.68	493.68
0.65	10,000	430.41	700.28
0.75	35,000	196.18	729.64
0.85	5,000	890.82	932.50

Table 1: Analysis Flight Conditions

4.1 Nonlinear Responses

The resulting longitudinal and lateral directional linear parameter varying controllers were implemented into the nonlinear FORTRAN simulation. In each case, at each time step the state space matrices are recomputed. To meet handling qualities requirements, a prefilter is added to the command path of each axis.

The spoiler slot deflectors and leading edge flaps allow deflection in one direction only because of physical considerations. For simplicity, these surfaces were not used in this implementation. Furthermore, the all moving tips are restricted to deflection in one direction only for secondary reasons, although physically they are able to deflect in both and wind tunnel data exist for both. Hence, it is assumed here that deflection is allowed in both directions.

To translate the generalized commands δ^*

$$\delta^* = [q_c \ p_c \ r_c]^T$$

into the individual surface commands δ , where

$$\delta = [\delta_{le} \ \delta_{re} \ \delta_{pf} \ \delta_{lamt} \ \delta_{ramt} \ \delta_{ptv} \ \delta_{yiv}]^T$$

a control selector is used. The control effectiveness matrix B is evaluated using interpolation between the linear points in Figure 1. The control selector matrix is computed as $\delta = B^\dagger B^* \delta^*$, where B^\dagger is the pseudo-inverse.

A coupled maneuver consisting of a four second pitch command of $5deg/sec$ followed by a four second roll doublet of $20deg/sec$ is simulated at each of the flight conditions. The pitch and roll controlled variables, as well as the angles of attack and sideslip, are shown in Figure 4. The large pitch overshoot is caused by the addition of lead into the command path via the pitch prefilter, which varies with flight condition.

Figure 4: Nonlinear Response

4.2 Robustness

Structured singular values are used to analyze the robust stability and robust performance of the LPV control laws for the points in Table 1. For robust stability, structured parameter uncertainty consisted of perturbations in the parameters Z_α , M_α , L_β , and N_β of 0.1, 1.0, 0.5, and 0.2, respectively, in either direction. The control selector is included, and fourth order actuator dynamics are included

for each of the actuators. In addition, unstructured uncertainty at the plant input is represented with a dynamic weight of

$$W_{unc}(s) = \frac{s+1}{5s+100}.$$

For robust performance, a model matching error is formed and weighted by

$$W_{err}(s) = \frac{100}{s^2 + 14s + 100},$$

in addition to the structured and unstructured uncertainty. The structured singular value plots are shown in Figure 5. This suggests that the LPV control law is robust to model uncertainty.

Figure 5: Structured Singular Values

5 Conclusions

The linear parameter varying control design procedure of [3, 4, 5] was used to develop a straightforward approach for the design of an automatically gain scheduled flight control law for the tailless aircraft. The use of a control selector allows the control design task to be done separately from the control allocation task. The resulting control design represents a good preliminary flight control law for the tailless aircraft. The model used in this paper provided a higher level of fidelity than that of [13] and hence provided better performance at the cost of computation time.

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